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Abstract: In this article, information is given about the movement communication, that is, body language and when the first study of body language began.

Key words: body language, kinesics, action communication, gestures, facial expressions, movement.

Body language is the transmission of messages or signals through non-verbal communication such as eye contact, facial expressions, gestures, and body posture. It includes social cues, movement, the distance between two people and the physical environment, and the use of freedom of appearance, touch, and sound. Gestures have three different parts, including the main gestures, i.e., the purpose of the signals delivered through gestures and the manner in which the receiver interprets them depends on his knowledge and feelings. In addition, gestures include the use of time and eye contact, gaze movements while speaking and listening, the number of gazes, pupil dilation, and blink rate.

Body language is a type of communication in which physical behaviors, as opposed to words, are used to express or convey information. Such behavior includes facial expressions, body posture, gestures, eye movement, touch and the use of space. The term body language is usually applied in regard to people but may also be applied to animals. The study of body language is also known as kinesics. Although body language is an important part of communication, most of it happens without conscious awareness.

The study of motor communication began in 1872 with Charles Darwin's *The Expression of Emotions in Man and Animals*. ("The Expression of Emotions in Man and Animals") began with the publication. Darwin began studying non-verbal communication because he saw animals like lions, tigers, dogs, etc. interacting and thus communicating through gestures and expressions. puts forward the idea, so he was one of the first to start this research.

Today, scientists argue that action communication can convey more meaning than verbal communication. Some scientists have proven that most people trust non-

verbal forms of communication more than verbal communication. It is concluded that gestural communication constitutes 60-70% of human communication, although other researchers: the type of communication cannot be determined and modern humans do not rely on gestures and especially this is developing day by day and more written evidence. although they have advanced the idea that such gestures do not reflect communication in the age of great importance.

Body language differs from sign language, which are languages with complex grammar systems and exhibiting the fundamental properties considered to exist in all true languages. Body language, on the other hand, does not have a grammar system and must be interpreted broadly, instead of having an absolute meaning corresponding with a certain movement. It is, technically, not a language. Body language more so refers to the often unconscious reactions we tend to have in relation to observed stimuli.

Within a society, consensus exists regarding the accepted understandings and interpretations of specific behaviors. There also is controversy on whether body language is universal. Body language, a subset of nonverbal communication, complements verbal communication in social interaction. In fact, some researchers conclude that nonverbal communication accounts for the majority of information transmitted during interpersonal interactions. It helps to establish the relationship between two people and regulates interaction, yet it can be ambiguous. The interpretation of body language tends to vary in different cultural contexts.

Body language is a major contributor to the attitude a person conveys to others. Albert Mehrabian maintains that during a conversation dealing with feelings and attitudes (i.e., like-dislike), 7% of what is communicated is via what is said, 38% is via tone of voice, and the majority, 55%, is via body language. This is also referred to as the '7%–38%–55% Rule', and is often considered in studies of human communications. While there is a wider debate about the percentage share which should be attributed to each of the three contributing factors, it is generally agreed upon that body language plays a fundamental role in determining the attitude a person conveys.

A person may alter their body language in order to alter the attitude they convey; this may in turn influence the rapport they have with another person. Whether a formal or informal attitude is conveyed may influence the other person's response. For instance, if an interviewer conveys a formal attitude, then this gives a more business-like impression, which may encourage the interviewee to give more serious answers. This may develop a more professional rapport overall between them.

Kinesics is the study and interpretation of nonverbal communication related to the movement of any part of the body or the body as a whole; in layman's terms, it is

the study of body language. However, Ray Birdwhistell, who is considered the founder of this area of study, never used the term body language, and did not consider it appropriate. He argued that what can be conveyed with the body does not meet the linguist's definition of language.

Birdwhistell pointed out that "human gestures differ from those of other animals in that they are polysemic, that they can be interpreted to have many different meanings depending on the communicative context in which they are produced". And, he "resisted the idea that 'body language' could be deciphered in some absolute fashion". He also indicated that "every body movement must be interpreted broadly and in conjunction with every other element in communication".

Despite that, body language is still more widely used than kinesics. Dr. Maziar Mir in his book *Body Language of Iran*, has defined body language as follows: to all gestures, postures, movements, human behaviour, body gestures, and even model and gesture of speaking, or all postures of making sounds without making a sound that is based on the age, sex, height, weight, and social or geographical status of human beings are referred to as body language or non-verbal communication.

REFERENCES:

1. Poyatos, Fernando (2002). *Nonverbal Communication Across Disciplines*, Volume II. John Benjamins Publishing Company. p. 189. [ISBN 1-55619-754-3](#).
2. Fast, Julius (2014). "1. The Body is the Message". *Body Language*. Open Road Media.
3. Klimt, Edward S.; & Belling, Ursula. (1979). *The signs of language*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. [ISBN 0674807952](#).
4. *The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals*. AMS Pres, 1972.
5. Candler, Wendy; & Lille-Martin, Diane. (2006). *Sign Language and Linguistic Universals.*: Cambridge University Press.
6. Mehrabian, Albert (2009). ["'Silent Messages' – A Wealth of Information About Nonverbal Communication \(Body Language\)"](#). *Personality & Emotion Tests & Software: Psychological Books & Articles of Popular Interest*. Los Angeles: self-published. Retrieved October 23, 2018
7. Danesi, M (2006). "Kinesics". *Encyclopedia of Language & Linguistics*. pp. 207–213. [doi:10.1016/B0-08-044854-2/01421-8](#). [ISBN 978-0080448541](#).